

A ROBUST ULTRASONIC OPTIMIZATION OF INDOOR NETWORK THROUGH WALL COMMUNICATION USING MIMO-OFDM

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to explore the use of ultrasonic technology for indoor data transmission over metallic obstacles at high rates. In order to decrease throughput-limiting crosstalk, such as the error rate, MIMO-OFDM is used in combination with interference mitigation strategies. For the general case of A transmitters and A receivers ($A \times A$ MIMO), several solutions for reducing crosstalk are examined, and their theoretical and practical bit-loaded data rates are calculated. Each transmitter-receiver pair is coaxially aligned on opposite sides of the metallic barrier (indoor applications within

range), and the transducers are positioned near together to study the effects of crosstalk. The use of innovative low power allocation methods in a MIMO-OFDM acoustic-electric channel is also explored in this article. These methods outperform the more traditional bit-loading and greedy bit-filling approaches in terms of throughput. Last but not least, this article details research on how transducer misalignment impacts bit-loading data transmission speeds and multichannel theoretical capacity. In order to improve the signal-to-noise ratio (throughput analysis) and decrease the minimum mean square error, the suggested method is a low-complexity design.

1. INTRODUCTION

The field of wireless technology has made remarkable strides in the last few years. In an attempt to get greater speeds of data transfer. Complex modulation methods, include orthogonal

Radio frequency (RF) communication lines that can handle data speeds in the 100s of Mbps have been made possible by combining frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) with multichannel methods like multiple input-multiple-output (MIMO). Data wireless communication via metallic

obstacles using ultrasonic has recently been the subject of research. Data transmission rates reported for successful implementations up to this point are fewer than 15 Mbps, which is much lower than the speeds attained in the wireless air channel. The acoustic-electric channel's frequency selectivity, or multipath echoes, causes substantial intersymbol interference (ISI), which is the main cause of these poor data rates.

The most up-to-date findings, which demonstrated the quasi-static character of the acoustic-electric channel, are given in [8]. Using the channel gain matrix's unique qualities, which are a consequence of this discovery, the transceiver design may be simplified while still passing strong metallic barriers with near-optimal throughput performance.

The following new contributions elevate this work above the current state of the art: 1) Shows how greedy bit-filling methods are used to the 7×7

by comparing the possible rates in the MIMO-OFDM acoustic electric channel to the bit-loading findings in [8], which demonstrate that, for a given modulation level, greedy bit filling performs better than standard bit loading strategies.

2) In the 7×7 MIMO-OFDM acoustic-electric channel, it introduces a new algorithm for allocating power that outperforms traditional methods like greedy bit filling and bit loading in terms of capacity. 3. Determined that misalignment of the transmit and receive transducers significantly reduces performance compared to when they are coaxially aligned, and examined the effect of misalignment on the achievable data rates for various interference mitigation structures. 4) Demonstrates that the use of different interference mitigation approaches leads to notable improvements in the attainable throughput performance, even when the transmitter and receiver transducers are significantly misaligned along their coaxial lines.

CHANNEL FORMATION AND MEASUREMENT

This would result in well conditioned channel gain matrices, lending well to simple crosstalk cancellation structures which do not require feedback. To investigate the

characteristics of the MIMO acoustic- electric channel a 7×7 MIMO configuration was formed, consisting of seven pairs of coaxially aligned piezoelectric transducers mounted on opposing sides of a 40 mm (1.575 in) thick steel barrier using Araldite 2014 epoxy. Each transducer has a 10 mm (0.394 in) diameter, 4 MHz nominal resonance frequency and is composed of APC850 material (APC International Ltd., Mackeyville, PA).

Fig:1.1 Transducer configuration dimensions for the hexagonal closed packed 7×7 MIMO acoustic- electric channel array.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Conformability to the fluctuating wireless channel is the foundation of a wireless link's spectrum efficiency. By choosing the coding and modulation scheme according to the channel state information, adaptive modulation and coding (AMC) allows multiple-input, multiple-output orthogonal frequency division multiplexing links to maximise performance under packet error rate constraints. With the effects of OFDM modulation and MIMO processing in mind,

complex MIMO-OFDM systems with error control coding, bit interleaving, and frequency selective channels are difficult to

model. Therefore, in order to simplify the models of the systems, the earlier AMC methods used approximations. Although these simplified models are helpful, they do not capture all of the system characteristics, which impacts the accompanying AMC techniques.

Despite being simpler and less optimal than its power-scaled counterpart, non-adaptive modulation techniques offer significantly higher data rates than non-adaptive bit loading, according to the final results of an analysis of the ABL implementation's measured performance. By utilising subcarrier-based rate adaptation in the ultrasonic channel, throughput rates can be increased by approximately 240% compared to traditional narrowband modulation techniques, all while maintaining the desired BER constraint of 10^{-5} , when the average PPSNR (post processing signal to noise ratio) is around 20 dB.

John D. Ashdown, G. J. Saulnier, S. Pascarelle, K. R. Wilt, H. A. Scarton, and J. D. Pinezich [3] are the authors. A new wireless system has been introduced that can send data and up to 50 W of AC power via a 63.5 mm (2.5 in) thick steel cable at 12.4 Mbps with a bit error rate (BER) below 10^{-6} .

hurdle. If required, a more powerful PA should allow the system's power transmission connection to achieve greater maximum power delivery.

G. J. Saulnier, T. J. Lawry, K. R. Wilt, and H. A. Scarton, [8] were authors. We showcased a seven-channel, high-rate ultrasonic through-wall communication system featuring Each channel has a bandwidth of 4.28 MHz. Theoretical capacity performance reaches 700 Mbps, as shown using measured channel data and MIMO- OFDM methods. Using the whole 7 MHz bandwidth per channel allows for even larger capacity. Data rates more than 50% of capacity were achieved by using realistic bit-loading strategies.

Written by T. J. Lawry, K. R. Wilt, J. D. Ashdown, G. J. Saulnier, and H. A. Scarton, [11]A device that can transport data and up to 50 W of alternating current at speeds of up to 17.37 Mbps through a steel barrier that is 63.5 mm thick has been shown. The device also has a bit error rate (BER) below 10^{-6} . If a more stronger power amplifier (PA) is wanted, the system's power transmission connection should be able to accomplish greater maximum power delivery.

A bidirectional communication connection might be simply added to this system, opening the door to a plethora of additional technologies, sensors, and

systems that may be securely upgraded for use in various critical aerospace, commercial,

military, and industrial applications. Additionally, it should be mentioned that much of the hardware was prototyped utilising large evaluation boards and connectorized commercial off-the-shelf components. Nevertheless, the whole system is not very complicated and may be significantly reduced in size if manufactured on a big scale.

3. SYSTEM DESIGN AND RESOURCE ALLOCATION OFDM-MIMO SYSTEMS

Since MIMO-OFDM provides the maximum spectrum efficiency and hence gives the largest capacity and data throughput, it is the cornerstone for most sophisticated wireless local area network (Wireless LAN) and mobile broadband network standards. Since OFDM partitions a high-speed data channel into many parallel, lower-speed channels, Raleigh hypothesised (and subsequently shown) that it would be more practical to utilise OFDM modulation to handle the processing demands of MIMO at greater speeds. The contemporary definition of "MIMO" encompasses more than only the use of several transmit antennas (multiple input) and multiple

hear antennas (with many outputs). The acronym "MIMO" stands for "multiple-input, multiple-

output," which maximises capacity by transmitting numerous signals at once (spatial multiplexing), as opposed to beamforming and diversity, which both make use of multiple reception antennas.

One of the core ideas behind MIMO wireless systems space-time signal processing in which time (the natural dimension of digital communication data) is complemented with the spatial dimension inherent in the use of multiple spatially distributed antennas, i.e. the use of multiple antennas located at different points. Accordingly MIMO wireless systems can be viewed as

a logical extension to the smart antennas that have been used for many years to improve wireless.

CAPACITY OF MIMO-OFDM SYSTEMS

Letting M denote the number of subcarriers, the capacity of the corresponding OFDM system can be expressed as

$$C_{ofdm} = \sum_{m=1}^M C_m$$

Where C_m denotes the underlying channel capacity of each subcarrier. Assuming an $A \times A$ MIMO array is adopted, the

received signal vector at the m^{th} subcarrier, Y_m , can be expressed as

$$Y_m = H_m X_m + \Omega_m$$

Where H_m denotes the $A \times A$ channel matrix, X_m denotes the $A \times 1$ transmitted signal vector and Ω_m denotes the $A \times 1$ noise vector whose elements are Gaussian random variables at the m^{th} subcarrier. Note that the $A \times A$ channel matrix H_m may be denoted by the entries $h_{ij}^{(m)}$ where i and j correspond to the j^{th} transmitter, respectively.

The capacity of a MIMO Gaussian channel is characterized. To be specific for a fixed channel matrix H_m , the mutual information between X_m and Y_m is given by

$$I(H_m, K_x) = B \log \det \left(I_A + \frac{1}{N_0 B} K_x H_m^* H_m \right)$$

Where H_m^* denotes the conjugate transpose of the channel matrix H_m , K_x is the correlation matrix of the transmitted symbols $K_x = E[X_m X_m^*]$, B is the bandwidth for each subcarrier and N_0 is the power spectral density of the noise.

, of the underlying MIMO channel for the m^{th} subcarrier is defined as

$$C_m = \max_{K_x: Tr[K_x] \leq P^{(m)}} I(H_m, K_x)$$

Where $P^{(m)}$ is the transmission power for the m^{th} subcarrier. When the channel state information is available at the transmitter, it is shown in [12], [13] that water-filling is the optimal power allocation. That is C_m can be expressed as

$$C_m = \frac{B}{N_0 B} \sum_{i=1}^A \log \left(1 + \frac{\lambda_i P_i^{(m)}}{N_0 B} \right)$$

Where λ_i is the i^{th} unordered eigenvalue of $H_m^* H_m$, and $P_i^{(m)}$ is the corresponding transmission power satisfying the water-filling condition $P_i^{(m)} = [\mu - 1/\lambda_i]^+$, where $[x]^+$ is the function with $[x]^+ = 0$ when $x < 0$ and $[x]^+ = x$ when $x \geq 0$. μ is the Lagrange multiplier obtained by solving

$$\sum_{i=1}^A P_i^{(m)} = P^{(m)}$$

To achieve the MIMO capacity in (5), the eigenmode transmission structure is used. To be specific the singular value decomposition (SVD) is conducted on the H_m

$$H_m = U_m \mathbf{\Sigma} V_m^H$$

Where $(\cdot)^H$ denotes the Hermitian complex conjugate transpose matrix operator, U_m and V_m are unitary receiver shaping and transmit precoding matrices, respectively, and $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ is diagonal matrix

with element ε_i denoting the i^{th} singular value of H_m . Note that $\lambda_i = \varepsilon_i^2$.

TRANSMIT PRECODING AND RECEIVE PROCESSING

In eigenmode transmission, the column vectors of V are used as transmit precoding vectors while the column vectors of U are used as receive beamforming vectors. In this way, different data streams will go through parallel “effective channels” not interfering with each other. Another popular transmit precoding strategy is called zero-forcing precoding where the transmitter tries to invert the underlying MIMO channel to create non-interfering parallel channels.

Fig 3.2 Eigenmode Transmission structure

Alternatively, the identity matrix can be used at the transmitter while the MMSE based transceiver [14], [16] can be employed. The objective of the MMSE approach is to minimize the average mean-square error between the

FLOW CHART OF BIT-LOADING

transmitted signal and the detected signal at the output of the structure. The MMSE output is formed by pre-scaling the received symbol vector by a weight matrix W having elements w_{ij} . The decision variable for the MMSE decoder is $z = Wy$. Assuming that the transmit signals are uncorrelated, signal and noise are uncorrelated, noise at the receivers is correlated, and that the transmit signals have unity power, an expression for the weight matrix is obtained as [17], [18]

$$W = [(HH^H + D)^{-1}H]^H$$

Where D is a diagonal matrix of noise variance terms. The symbols at the output of the MMSE structure are written as

$$Z = WHX + W\eta$$

POWER ALLOCATION

TECHNIQUES

BIT LOADING TECHNIQUE:

The idea behind bit-loading is to load each OFDM subcarrier with the largest number of bits it can support given its receive SNR level and a target BER. The transmit power on the sub channels that exceed the required SNR to support the highest chosen modulation level can be reduced such that the receive SNR of these subcarriers exactly meets the required level to achieve the target BER.

Fig 3.4 initialization sequence for bit-loading and power allocation

In this section, the data rate performance utilizing bit-loading techniques is compared to the achievable rate performance results of the previous sections. In this analysis, each channel has a 4.28 MHz bandwidth and a target bit error rate (BER) of 10^{-6} is used. Each OFDM subcarrier on each channel is loaded with the highest order modulation that supports a BER of 10^{-6} or lower.

At an average SNR level of 45 dB, significant throughput improvement using bit-loading occurs as the highest modulation level is increased from BPSK to 1024-QAM. Beyond 1024-QAM, the gains in throughput are relatively marginal. This bit-loading approach provides data rates up to and exceeding 50% of the theoretical capacity and is further described in [8].

**GREEDY BIT-FILLING
TECHNIQUE**

This ensures that the receiver's SNR for each bit-carrying OFDM sub-channel will precisely match the level needed to achieve the desired BER. The greedy bit-filling method is shown in Figure 3.5 as a block diagram.

greedy bit-filling, rate-neutral power saving, and rate-increase electrical consumption.

Following the procedure shown in Figure 3.5, the first step is to fill all of the channels with bits greedily. After selecting the maximum modulation level, greedy bit filling is carried out.

**FLOW CHART OF GREEDY BIT
FILLING TECHNIQUE**

Fig 3.5 Block Diagram of Greedy Bit-Filling Routine

**NOVEL POWER ALLOCATION
TECHNIQUE**

Compared to bit-loading and greedy bit-filling, our innovative power allocation method enables the use of many modulation levels and considerably increases the available data speeds. An intricate section

The power allocation process, shown in Figure 3.5, is comprised of three primary parts:

**NOVEL POWER ALLOCATION
TECHNIQUE FLOW CHART**

Fig 3.6 Block diagram of power allocation routine

4. PROPOSED TECHNIQUE

INTRODUCTION

Now a day efficient frequency spectrum utilization is very serious problem because number users and applications is increased. Different modulation techniques and different algorithms used to provide channels to all users. Proposed technique is designed by greedy power allocation technique. MIMO-OFDM is an efficient technique for achieving high downlink capacity in high-speed communication system. A key issue in MIMO-OFDM is the allocation of the OFDM subcarriers and power to users sharing channel. Subcarriers and power allocation are carried out sequentially to reduce complexity.

The low complexity proportional subcarriers allocation is followed by greedy power allocation to solve the rate-adaptive resource allocation problem with proportional rate constraints for MIMO-OFDM systems. Greedy power allocation achieves approximate rate proportionality while maximizing the total sum-rate capacity MIMO-OFDM.

GREEDY POWER ALLOCATION TECHNIQUE

After the available subcarriers are proportionally allocated to the users, a GPA algorithm is proposed to optimally

allocate the transmit power between the allocated subcarriers to maximize the sum-rate capacity of the MIMO-OFDM . The GPA algorithm of the MIMO-OFDM system can be described by the following steps.

Step1:Determine the number of subcarriers N_k to be initially assigned to each user

Step 2: Assign the subcarriers to each user in a way that ensures rough proportionality

Step 3: Assign the total power P_K for user k to maximize the capacity, while enforcing the proportionality.

Step 4: Assign the powers $P_{k,n}$ for each user's subcarriers subject to his total power constraint P_k .

PROCEDURE

- 1) Calculate the power of each user in the MIMO-OFDM system as follows

$$P_K = \sum_{n=1}^N C_{K,n} P_{K,n}$$

- 2) The problem of subcarriers and power allocation for the MIMO-OFDM system is simplified into the problem of power allocation for a multi-user OFDM system.

$$\max_{P_{K,n}} \frac{1}{N} \sum C_{K,n} \log_2(1 + P_{K,n} H_{K,n})$$

$$\forall K \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$$

$$H_{k,n} = \frac{h_{k,n}}{\Gamma} \text{ is effective subcarrier SNR.}$$

$$\Gamma = \ln \frac{(5BER)}{1.6} \text{ is a constant SNR gap}$$

$$h_{k,n} = g_{kn}^2 / \sigma^2, \quad \sigma^2 = \frac{N_0 B}{N}$$

Where

$$h_{k,n} = \text{Subcarrier SNR}$$

with total user power budget P_K , target BER, and maximum permissible QAM modulation order. These constraints can be formulated as

$$\sum_{n=1}^N C_{k,n} P_{k,n} \leq P_K$$

$$P_{b,n} = BER$$

$$r_n \leq r^{max}$$

$$BER_{MQAM}(\gamma_{k,n}) = 0.2 \exp\left(\frac{-16\gamma_{k,n}}{\Gamma}\right)$$

$$r_{k,n} = \log\left(1 + \frac{\gamma_{k,n}}{\Gamma}\right) = \log\left(1 + \frac{P_{k,n} H_{k,n}}{\sigma^2}\right)$$

Where

$r_{k,n} = K^{th}$ user's received SNR on subcarrier n

$$r_{k,n} = P_{k,n} h_{k,n}$$

Where $P_{k,n}$ is the amount of power allocated to the n^{th} subcarrier of k^{th} user to achieve a BER $P_{b,n}$, and γ^{max} is maximum number of permissible allocated bits per subcarrier. Note that BERs are assumed equal that is $P_{b,n} = BER, \forall n \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ and therefore the subscript n will be dropped from BER notation to become P_b .

2) The problem of power allocation for subcarrier in the MIMO-OFDM system is

solved by the GPA algorithm that is summarized follows

- a) Calculate γ_l^{QAM} for all $M_l, 1 \leq l \leq L$ and $P_{b,n} = BER$ where γ_l^{QAM} is the SNR of QAM level is permissible by the transmission system that is $M = \gamma_l^{max}$
- b) Redistribute subcarriers according to their SNRs $\gamma_{k,n}$ into QAM groups $G_l, 0 \leq l \leq L$ bounded by QAM levels γ_l^{QAM} and γ_{l+1}^{QAM} with $\gamma_0^{QAM} = 0, \gamma_l^{QAM} = +\infty, \gamma_l^{QAM} \leq \gamma_{k,n} \leq \gamma_{l+1}^{QAM}$
- 4) The GPA algorithm is repeated for all users to calculate the sum rate capacity of the MIMO-OFDM system.

$$R^{gpa} = \sum_{k=1}^K R_k^{gpa}$$

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This paper is implemented for transmitting high wireless data through metallic enclosure by using matlab software. The experimental results shown in below figures.

Fig 5.1: Achievable rate of 7x7 MIMO acoustic electrical channel array (under measured weak crosstalk)

Fig 5.2: Achievable rate of 7x7 MIMO acoustic electrical channel array (under enhanced / strong crosstalk)

Fig 5.5: seven channel capacity, power allocation, bit loading and greedy power allocation performance comparisons

Fig 5.3: 7x7 MIMO 4.28 MHz bandwidth bit loading and greedy power allocation performance comparisons (MMSE)

Fig 5.6: Three channel sub array coaxial (direct) transducer alignment and 4.28 MHz bandwidth per channel.

Fig 5.4: seven channel capacity, Bit loading, greedy bit filling, novel power allocation and Greedy power allocation Performance comparisons (MMSE).

Fig 5.7: Three channel sub array transducer misalignment and 4.28 MHz bandwidth Per channel

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

This research explored and evaluated several methods for maximising data rates in an effort to bring the possible data rates closer to the capacity. In particular, we looked at the innovative power allocation method and the greedy bit filling methodology, both of which demonstrate a significant gain in attainable rate compared to the bit-loading strategy. Coaxial misalignment between the transducers of the transmitters and the receivers is another area that needs investigation. When compared to the other methods, the greedy power allocation algorithm that was suggested produced far better throughput performance and had the lowest mean square error.

Transmitting high-speed wireless data via a metallic enclosure with a constant bit error rate of 10^{-6} and a 4.28MHz channel bandwidth is the subject of this research. Using frequency allocation methods, we can cut the bit error rate to less than 10^{-6} , decrease the bandwidth to less than 4.28 MHz while maintaining the same data throughput, and expand the channel length and size to transmit more data at once.

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